
Bridging Educational Gaps: Designing Transitional Learning Hubs for the Students Residing In the Mountainous Barangays of Naguilian, La Union

Christine S. Estioco¹ and Winona Elaine C. Soriano²

¹BS. Architecture, College of Engineering and Architecture, Saint Louis College, La Union

²Faculty of Architecture, College of Engineering and Architecture, Saint Louis College, La Union

ABSTRACT

Students in the mountainous barangays of Naguilian, La Union, face significant challenges in accessing education during inclement weather due to the region's vulnerability to flooding and landslides caused by typhoons. This study investigated the geographical factors that hinder students' access to education, focusing on those living far from school and located in hazard-prone areas. A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining spatial analysis using Geographic Information System (GIS) software to identify the optimal location for the proposed transitional learning hub located in mountainous regions of Naguilian and qualitative data gathered through surveys and interviews with students and community members. This approach allowed for a comprehensive understanding of physical and social barriers to educational access. The study revealed that students residing in mountainous regions of Naguilian are having difficulties accessing the nearby school during and after natural hazards. Minor rainfall was found to create impassable road conditions in certain areas, particularly along routes going to school. This situation makes it difficult for students who rely on walking in such dangerous

conditions. Thus, this study proposed the establishment of transitional learning hubs in Naguilian, La Union, which aim to serve as a medium for maintaining students' access to educational opportunities during disruptions caused by inclement weather and serve as a model for adaptable learning environments in other underserved and hazard-prone regions. By integrating community and vernacular architecture principles, the design emphasizes cost-effectiveness, disaster-resiliency, and environmental sustainability, tailored to the unique geographical conditions of Naguilian. This research advocates for a proactive design approach that prioritizes educational environments responsive to the needs of communities facing environmental challenges.

Keywords: Community architecture, critical Regionalism, disaster-resilient, transitional learning hub, vernacular architecture

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines ranked number one among the countries with the highest risks worldwide in terms of natural disasters and extreme weather conditions, with an index of 46.86 (World Risk Report, 2023). This is mainly due to the location and geographical context, as the risk of coastal hazards such as typhoons, storm surges, and rising sea levels is high. Also, as the islands are located within the "Ring of Fire," earthquakes and volcanoes pose severe risks to the safety of the people (CFE-DM, 2018). Natural disasters often damage infrastructure, disrupt education and health services, and destroy homes and personal belongings, making life harder for many families (World Bank Group, 2023). These are all significant ongoing threats that regularly disrupt education in the Philippines. Children suffer from the global learning crisis, which has been identified as having limited access to quality education, according to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural

Organization.

One of the critical challenges schools face during disasters is the impact on students living far from the school, especially those who live in mountainous regions. One of the primary concerns of students living far from school during a disaster is the risk of travel. Unpredictable occurrences of disasters can expose students to various hazards as they commute to and from school, potentially leading to injuries, loss of life, or property damage. In natural or artificial disasters, students living far from their schools face significant challenges that disrupt their access to education, limiting their ability to attend classes and participate in learning (Mirzaei, 2019).

Approximately 78 percent of public schools and 96 percent of students in the Philippines are exposed and vulnerable to multiple hazards. Between 2021 and 2023, around 4,000 schools were damaged due to various disasters, disrupting learning continuity for two million children. (World Bank Group, 2023). The Philippines faces frequent natural disasters that disrupt the school calendar and limit access to education, especially for students living far from schools (Symaco, 2013).

Disasters have caused widespread damage to infrastructure, including schools, and have resulted in the temporary or permanent closure of educational institutions. As a result, students have experienced significant disruptions to their education, which can lead to lower academic achievement and, ultimately, lower IQ scores (Reinman, 2015). The adverse effects of these disruptions somehow contribute to the Philippines' low ranking in global average IQ assessments, ranked 111th out of 199 countries with an average IQ score of 81.64 for 2023, which puts us on the outside looking in compared to some of our other Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) counterparts (World Population Review, 2024).

La Union is composed of coastal and mountainous regions; it covers five circuits: Northern, Central Central, Eastern, South, and Southeastern circuits. The Central Eastern La Union consists of municipalities located in mountainous areas, such as Bagulin, Burgos, and Naguilian; only Bauang is near the coast.

According to the Provincial Government of La Union, Naguilian is the most prone to natural hazards, comprising 37 barangays alongside Bauang and Bagulin. Naguilian is exposed to hydrometeorological hazards such as flooding, rain-induced landslides, and tension cracks triggered by solid typhoons, which bring heavy monsoon rains caused by forest denudation, lack of vegetation cover in steep areas, and loose soil along riverbanks and creeks. Naguilian is considered a high risk of typhoons and earthquakes (figures 1 & 2) (DENR, 2024; PHIVOLCS, 2024). For the last three years, flooding has been the most common hazard that affects almost all barangays, with a high susceptibility to flooding and landslides (figure 4), and some of the Barangays are also susceptible to liquefaction (figure 3). The population that is exposed and vulnerable to rain-induced landslides comprises twenty-three (23) barangays mainly located near mountains and creeks. (PGLU,2024).

Figure 1. Risk to typhoons: All areas in Naguilian have a very high risk of typhoons (DENR, 2021)

Figure 2. Ground Shaking hazard map of Naguilian, color red indicating Intensity VIII or higher: Very Destructive (PHIVOLCS,2022)

Figure 3. Liquefaction Hazard Map of Naguilian, La Union, color yellow indicating areas that are prone to liquefaction (PHIVOLCS,2022)

Figure 4. Geohazard map of Naguilian, La Union

(Image: from Planning and Development Office of Naguilian)

Education is a fundamental right, but geographical and environmental factors often create barriers for students in far-flung areas (Torres,2024; Bicar et al.,2020). Within this context

of high disaster risk, education in Naguilian faces particular challenges, especially in mountainous regions where geographical and environmental factors create significant barriers for students. Naguilian is highly susceptible to flooding and landslides (*figure 3*), which often make roads impassable and pose dangers to students traveling to school. Teachers report that during and after typhoons, many students are unable to attend classes. For instance, at Eastern Naguilian National High School (ENNHS), almost half of the students from barangay Al-Alinao Sur cannot attend school during typhoons. Even mild or heavy rain can create challenges, as roads become muddy and difficult to traverse, particularly for students who must walk long distances to school.

Transitional learning hubs significantly impact disaster-affected communities by serving as catalysts for recovery and resilience. Beyond restoring education, these hubs provide immediate economic opportunities through local labor and material sourcing, equipping residents with valuable construction skills. They foster social cohesion by involving parents, teachers, and leaders in planning and maintenance, creating a sense of ownership and enhancing communal ties. Psychosocially, these hubs offer children safe, structured environments to rebuild routines. At the same time, parents gain peace of mind to focus on rebuilding their lives. Additionally, their emphasis on disaster risk reduction inspires safer reconstruction practices, promoting long-term resilience. Transitional learning hubs are more than educational spaces; they are vital centers of hope, unity, and progress for the communities they serve (UNICEF, 2013).

The creation of learning hubs is crucial to overcoming the barriers faced by students in this disaster-prone region. The proposed learning hubs will serve as a community center that supports educational learning and promotes disaster preparedness and environmental stewardship. This initiative will ensure that education remains accessible to all, regardless of geographical or environmental conditions, and will promote long-term sustainability within the community.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a mixed-methods approach, integrating qualitative and quantitative research methods, to guide the development of transitional learning hubs in the mountainous areas of Naguilian, La Union. This approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of the research problem by combining the strengths of both methodologies.

Research Design

Qualitative research methods explore the local community's needs and preferences, providing insights into the social and cultural context of the study. Semi-structured interviews will be conducted with various stakeholders, including students, parents, teachers, and community leaders (i.e., Barangay Captains and Barangay Health Workers). These interviews will explore perspectives on educational needs, disaster preparedness, and preferences for learning spaces. Surveys will be administered to gather educational experiences and preferences for learning hub features. Lastly, field observations were conducted to document existing educational facilities, infrastructure conditions (i.e., road network conditions), community spaces, and environmental conditions in the mountainous barangays. The qualitative research will be informed by Kenneth Frampton's theory of Critical Regionalism, which emphasizes the importance of balancing modern architectural practices with regional specificity. This will involve analyzing how local building traditions, materials, and environmental considerations can be integrated into the design of the learning hubs.

Quantitative research will focus on gathering empirical data to inform the design and location of the learning hubs. A geographic information system (GIS) is employed to analyze geographical data, including topography, hazard maps, and population density, to identify optimal locations for the learning hubs.

Research Locale

The research locale, which is the mountainous barangay of Naguilian, La Union, holds significant importance in this

study as it embodies the challenges faced by rural and disaster-prone communities in accessing quality education. Naguilian experiences frequent natural disasters, such as flooding and landslides, which make students residing in mountainous regions travel in risky situations and often prevent them from attending school. Additionally, during heavy rains, many of the routes to school become muddy and impassable, further complicating access to education. This geographical vulnerability necessitates the development of a community-based learning center that provides educational opportunities and incorporates resilience and sustainability into its design.

SITE SELECTION

Figure 9-10

Boundary Map of La Union (PGLU,2024)

The main goal of the study is to address the accessibility of education for students residing in far-flung areas, especially those located in mountainous regions experiencing different natural hazards. Topographic analysis was used to identify which region in La Union is mainly composed of mountainous regions (Figures 9 & 10). It is identified that Central Eastern La Union covers most mountainous regions compared to Southeastern, South, Northern, and Central La Union.

The main consideration in selecting a locale is identifying first which municipality in Central Eastern La Union is the most vulnerable to natural hazards. Naguilian, Bagulin, and Burgos are mountainous and forested areas. Only the Municipality of Bauang has a coastal area along a portion of the shoreline of the West Philippine Sea.

The **Municipality of Naguilian**, which comprises 37 barangays, is highly susceptible to hydrometeorological hazards, particularly flooding, rain-induced landslides, and tension cracks triggered by powerful typhoons that bring heavy monsoon rains. Naguilian and the broader province of La Union are especially vulnerable to landslides caused by factors such as forest denudation, insufficient vegetation cover in steep regions, and unstable soil along riverbanks and creeks. These environmental conditions primarily affect twenty-three barangays located near mountainous areas and creeks, leaving the population exposed to these hazards. Landslide occurrences often result in temporary road closures, severely impacting economic activity by hindering the movement of people and the transport of goods and services within Naguilian and nearby municipalities. Additionally, Naguilian is largely mountainous terrain and has a relatively high population density as it is a first-class municipality aiming to become a city.

Figure 11. Elevation map (topographic-map.com)

The project locale needs to be specific, so the barangays that are located in mountainous regions must be identified. Using the software QGIS and elevationmap.net, the barangays located in mountainous regions are identified. (Figures 11 & 12). In Figure 12, different colors are used to indicate the different elevations in Naguilian, La Union. Blue is considered flat land, while red indicates the uphill areas. In Naguilian, the color varies from blue to yellow-green, 10 meters to 510 meters. A region is defined as mountainous if its elevation varies by at least 300 meters, as shown in **Figure 11 Elevation Map** (*topographic-map.com*) identified as a hill if it is lower than 300 meters (Price, 2015). In Figure 13, barangays that are considered as hill and mountainous regions are identified. Dark blue indicates a barangay that is considered a mountainous region, while light blue represents uphill barangays.

Figure 12. Hill and Mountain regions in Naguilian La Union
(QGIS mapping)

In figures 13 and 14, different schools in Naguilian are reflected; it is evident that almost all of the barangays have elementary schools, while the secondary schools are located mostly in relatively flat areas.

The different areas that are reflected in Figure 16 are the areas that are likely to be impassable and challenging to traverse during the occurrence of natural hazards. These conditions significantly affect students' ability to attend school during and after a disaster, disrupting their school attendance and overall learning continuity.

District	BEIS	Schr	School Name	Barangay	Sectr	SY 2020-21	SY 2021-22	SY 2022-23	SY 2023-24	SY 2024-2025
Naguilian	400093	Holy Infant Niño Montessori and High School	NATIVIDAD (PCB)	Privat	180	170	171	164	CS	
Naguilian	400094	Naguilian Learning Center, Inc	IMELDA	Privat	75	84	96	78		71
Naguilian	400095	St. Augustine School of Naguilian, Inc.	NATIVIDAD (PCB)	Privat	112	86	93	92		93
Naguilian	410223	Philippine Central College of Arts & Science & Te	NATIVIDAD (PCB)	Privat	62				CLOSED SCHOOL (CS)	
Naguilian	41034	Naguilian Baptist Christian School, Inc.	ORTIZ (PCB)	Privat	7	33	61	107		114
Naguilian	41048	COLEGIO de LA UNION	NATIVIDAD (PCB)	Privat	115	93	100	114		83
Naguilian	100970	Al-Alinao ES	AL-ALINAO NOR	Public	157	158	132	121		96
Naguilian	100971	Ambaracao Sur Elementary School	AMBARACAO SU	Public	260	226	231	221		226
Naguilian	100972	Al-alinao Sur ES	AL-ALINAO SUR	Public	126	126	122	111		94
Naguilian	100973	Balecbeec ES	BALECBEEC	Public	111	103	95	101		94
Naguilian	100974	Bancagan ES	BANCAGAN	Public	127	123	116	107		106
Naguilian	100975	BARADAS SURELEM SCHOOL	BARADAS SUR	Public	201	197	206	200		198
Naguilian	100976	Bariquir Elementary School	BARIQUIR	Public	218	215	220	211		198
Naguilian	100977	Bato Elementary School	BATO	Public	134	181	177	177		160
Naguilian	100978	Lower Bimolobot ES	BIMMOTOBOT	Public	48	40	42	42		41
Naguilian	100979	Bimolobot 2 Upper PS	BIMMOTOBOT	Public	110	110	103	106		98
Naguilian	100981	Mamat-Ing Norte Elementary School	MAMAT-ING NOR	Public	81	72	67	66		64
Naguilian	100984	Don Tomas R. Mendoza ES	RIBSUAN	Public	256	240	233	227		204
Naguilian	100985	Dr. Hermogenes T. Belen ES	ORTIZ (PCB)	Public	202	182	196	249		232
Naguilian	100986	Guesset ES	GUESSET	Public	234	252	245	257		250
Naguilian	100987	Gusing ES	GUSING NORTE	Public	311	307	274	283		237
Naguilian	100988	Lioac ES	LIOAC SUR	Public	235	225	226	223		214
Naguilian	100989	Mamat-Ing Sur ES	MAMAT-ING SUR	Public	210	215	221	219		200
Naguilian	100990	Nagsidorisan ES	NAGSIDORISAN	Public	127	115	111	116		102
Naguilian	100991	Naguilian CS	ORTIZ (PCB)	Public	957	932	871	854		780
Naguilian	100992	San Antonio ES	SAN ANTONIO	Public	119	126	115	115		99
Naguilian	100993	San Isidro ES	SAN ISIDRO	Public	103	105	95	83		85
Naguilian	100995	Tudnggan ES	TUDNGGAN	Public	189	178	204	182		166
Naguilian	131154	AMADEO FLORENDO RIMANDO ELEMENTARY	AMBARACAO NC	Public	182	177	166	165		148
Naguilian	151006	Mangkaeng PS	GUSING NORTE	Public	35	36	30	30		23
Naguilian	281625	Baraas Norte Elementary School	BARADAS NOR	Public	115	108	108	90		89
Naguilian	300122	Naguilian National HS	IMELDA	Public	3044	3408	3376	2945		2966
Naguilian	300123	Northern Naguilian National High School	GUSING NORTE	Public	556	560	511	441		445
Naguilian	300144	Southern Naguilian National High School	AMBARACAO SU	Public	277	274	247	206		197
Naguilian	321005	Eastern Naguilian National High School	GUESSET	Public	372	376	374	335		346
Naguilian	340823	Naguilian Senior High School	ORTIZ (PCB)	Public	479	496	394	425		503
Naguilian	500355	Suguidan Integrated School	SUGUIDAN SUR	Public	209	205	196	175		159
Naguilian	500360	Daramulangan Integrated School	DARAMULANGAN	Public	357	353	312	310		294
Naguilian	500495	Casilagan Elementary School	CASILAGAN	Public	393	392	373	364		353
Naguilian	501362	Cabaritan Sur Integrated School	CABARITAN SUR	Public	406	460	465	466		445
									total	total
									1695	1109

Figure 13
Schools in Naguilian La Union (Deped,S.Y.2024-2025)

Figure 14

Location of Different Schools in Naguilian La Union (GIS mapping)

Figure 15

Impassable Routes During the Occurrence of Natural Hazards

In this study, which focuses on building transitional learning hubs in Naguilian, La Union, the need to have a deep understanding of the locale is fundamental. The region's

mountainous terrain, frequent natural hazards, and transportation challenges are major obstacles to students' access to the nearest school. These characteristics align closely with the research objectives, which aim to create transitional learning hubs that serve as a medium for students to continue their learning despite the occurrence of different natural hazards; these transitional learning hubs will be designed to be disaster-resilient, cost-effective, and environmentally sustainable.

By considering the specific geographical conditions of the area, the study aims to address the community's unique educational needs, particularly in reducing the impact of disasters on education. This understanding reinforces the need for infrastructure that can withstand natural calamities while fostering inclusivity and sustainability—key goals of the proposed solution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the findings of the study, focusing on the geographical challenges faced by the students residing in mountainous regions of Naguilian, La Union, in accessing education during and after natural hazards. Using spatial analysis and community insights, the study proposes transitional learning hubs as a resilient solution to address these disruptions. The results highlight the significance of disaster-resilient, cost-effective, and environmentally sustainable designs in ensuring continuous educational access while fostering local empowerment.

Table 1

Mountainous Barangays in Naguilian, La Union Affected by Natural Hazards That Hinder Student Access to Education

Barangay	Number of students (n)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Mamat-ing Norte	146	136	93.15
Bimmotobot	121	115	95.04
Gusing Norte	139	133	95.68
Casilagan	363	293	80.72
San Antonio	129	120	88.89
Al-Alinao Sur	135	125	92.59
Balebec	177	171	96.61
San Isidro	181	166	91.71

Mirzaei's (2019) study emphasizes that students living in mountainous areas face significant challenges during natural hazards, primarily due to the risks associated with traveling to school. The unpredictable occurrence of natural hazards frequently disrupts their access to education, making it harder for them to attend classes and engage in learning compared to students in lowland areas. As Table 1 illustrates, all barangays located in the mountainous region of Naguilian, La Union, have a high percentage of students facing limited access to school during and after natural hazards, underscoring the study's emphasis on the urgent need for resilient and accessible learning hubs. These findings highlight the widespread impact of natural hazards on education in the region, underscoring the importance of prioritizing safe, sustainable solutions to ensure educational continuity for affected students.

The following tables highlight the different natural hazards encountered by the students living in different barangays located in the mountainous region of Naguilian, La Union, which these natural hazards limit their access to school.

Legend

- a. Landslides
- b. Flooded roads or pathways
- c. Damaged bridges or infrastructure
- d. Eroded or muddy trails
- e. Long and unsafe travel routes

Table 2

Barangay Mamat-ing Norte

Table 2 shows that 40.41% of students in Brgy. Mamat-ing Norte is unable to attend classes during natural hazards due to landslides, flooded roads or pathways, eroded or muddy trails, and long, unsafe travel routes.

Table 3

Barangay Bimmotobot

Table 3 shows that 23.14% of students in Brgy. Bimmotobots are unable to attend classes during natural hazards, with landslides, flooded roads or pathways, eroded or muddy trails, and long, unsafe travel routes posing significant challenges.

Table 4

Barangay Gusing Norte

Table 4 shows that landslides and eroded or muddy trails prevent 44.4% of students in Brgy. Gusing Norte from attending classes during natural hazards.

Table 5

Barangay Casilagan

Table 5 shows that 24.24% of students in Brgy. Casilagan is unable to attend classes during natural hazards due to landslides, flooded roads or pathways, eroded or muddy trails, and long, unsafe travel routes.

Table 6

Barangay San Antonio

Table 6 shows that 15.5% of students in barangay San Antonio are unable to attend classes during typhoons due to hazards such as landslides, flooded roads or pathways, eroded or muddy trails, and damaged bridges, resulting in missed learning opportunities and hindering their educational progress.

Table 7
Barangay Al-Alinao Sur

Table 7 shows that 23.70% of students in Brgy. Al-Alinao Sur is unable to attend classes during natural hazards due to landslides, flooded roads or pathways, eroded or muddy trails, and long, unsafe travel routes.

Table 8
Barangay Balebec

Table 8 shows that 15.82% of students in Brgy. Balebec is unable to attend classes during natural hazards due to landslides, flooded roads or pathways, eroded or muddy trails, and long, unsafe travel routes.

Table 9

Barangay San Isidro

Table 9 shows that 44.88% of students in Brgy. San Isidro is unable to attend classes during natural hazards due to landslides and eroded or muddy trails.

Tables 2 to 9 reveal that the majority of the eight barangay studies face significant challenges in ensuring students' access to education during natural hazards. Five barangays—Casilagan, Bimmotobot, Mamat-ing Norte, Balebec, and Al-Alinao Sur—experience landslides, flooded roads, eroded trails, and unsafe travel routes. Two barangays, Gusing Norte and San Isidro, primarily encounter landslides and eroded trails. Only students in Barangay San Antonio face the additional risk of damaged bridges and infrastructure. These hazards pose serious risks to students, including injury and potential loss of life, as highlighted by Mirzaei (2019). Such disruptions to education are particularly concerning in the Philippines, where natural disasters frequently endanger lives and disrupt the school calendar, especially for students in mountainous areas (Symaco, 2013).

The impact of natural hazards on students' performance and overall educational progress

Figure 1. Shows the response of teachers in Naguilian, La Union, about the effect of frequent disruption of natural hazards on the academic performance of the students residing in mountainous areas.

Figure 1 illustrates that out of 170 teachers in Naguilian, La Union, a significant portion reported a decline in student performance due to natural hazards. Specifically, 71 teachers (41.8%) observed a significant decline, 89 teachers (52.4%) noted a moderate decline, and only 10 teachers (5.9%) reported an unnoticeable impact. This data highlights the substantial effect that natural hazards can have on the academic performance of students in mountainous regions. For example, when landslides block roads or floods inundate communities, students' regular attendance and learning are disrupted, leading to a decline in their performance (Potter et al., 2020).

Figure 2

Teachers' Observations on Learning Gaps Among Students in Naguilian, La Union Due to Missed Lessons Following Natural Hazard Events

Figure 2 illustrates that a majority of teachers in Naguilian, La Union, perceive a significant gap in students' knowledge following natural hazard events. Of the 170 teachers surveyed, 112 (65.9%) reported a significant gap in students' knowledge due to missed lessons, while 45 (26.5%) observed a manageable gap. A smaller portion, 12 teachers (7.1%),

identified minimal gaps, and only one teacher (0.6%) was not sure. This data underscores the challenges faced by students in mountainous areas, where natural hazards can disrupt their educational trajectories. Seasonal disruptions, such as floods or landslides, can prevent students from attending school, causing them to miss critical lessons and fall behind in their studies. This disparity in educational access can lead to widening gaps in academic performance and long-term educational outcomes (Boer & Asino, 2022).

Figure 3. Shows the response of teachers teaching in Naguilian, La Union, about how long it typically takes for students residing in mountainous areas to catch up on their missed lessons after natural hazard disruptions.

Figure 3 shows that a majority of teachers in Naguilian, La Union, believe it takes students one to two weeks to catch up on missed lessons after a natural hazard event. Of the 170 teachers surveyed, 99 (58.2%) estimated one to two weeks, while 41 (24.1%) estimated less than one week. However, a significant minority, 16 teachers (9.4%), felt it was difficult for students to catch up, and 14 (8.2%) estimated it would take more than two weeks.

Figure 4. Shows the response of the students residing in mountainous areas of Naguilian, La Union, about how long it typically takes for them to catch up on their missed lessons after natural hazard disruptions.

Figure 4 presents the students' perspectives, with 936 out of 1,401 students (66.8%) reporting that they can catch up on missed lessons within a week. In contrast, 418 students (29.8%) estimated it takes one to two weeks, and 44 students (3.1%) said it takes more than two weeks. Only three students (0.2%) felt they could not catch up. These findings highlight the discrepancy between teachers' and students' perceptions of the time required to recover from learning disruptions. While students tend to be more optimistic, a significant proportion of teachers express concern about the difficulty students face in catching up, especially after prolonged disruptions. This aligns with research indicating that students in mountainous regions often miss significant class time due to natural hazards (Uzenova et al., 2019; Wherli, 2014). When forced to miss school, students struggle to catch up, leading to academic setbacks and widening learning gaps (Uzdenova et al., 2019). Furthermore, the psychological impact of natural disasters, including stress, anxiety, and depression, can hinder students' ability to engage with their studies effectively (Agaton & Cueto, 2021; Atlam et al., 2021).

Figure 5

Student Responses from Mountainous Areas of Naguilian, La Union on the Impact of Frequent Natural Hazard Disruptions on Their Learning

Figure 5 illustrates that out of 1,401 students residing in mountainous areas of Naguilian, La Union, 617 students which are 44% responded that they missed a lot of lessons due to natural hazards, 524 students, which are 37.4%, responded that they have trouble keeping up with their studies, 205 students, which are 14.6%, responded that they feel stressed or distracted. In comparison, 55 students, which is 3.9%, responded that it does not affect them much. The prevalence of natural hazards in mountainous regions poses a significant challenge to students' education, as it often leads to missed lessons and gaps in their knowledge. These regions are highly susceptible to various natural disasters, which can disrupt the normal functioning of schools and prevent students from attending classes (Uzdenova et al., 2019).

Figure 6

Student Responses from Mountainous Areas of Naguilian, La Union on Experiencing Grade Declines Due to Natural Hazards

Figure 6 shows that a majority of the 1,401 students surveyed in mountainous areas of Naguilian, La Union, believe that natural hazards significantly affect their grades. Specifically,

725 students (51.7%) reported a significant drop in their grades due to natural hazards. In comparison, 593 students (42.3%) reported no significant drop, and 83 students (5.9%) were unsure.

These findings highlight the vulnerability of students living far from their schools to the academic consequences of natural disasters. When events like floods, earthquakes, or landslides occur, these students face greater challenges in attending school due to damaged infrastructure, road closures, or safety concerns, ultimately leading to a drop in their academic performance (Koerniadi et al., 2015; Ekuase-Anwansedo et al., 2021). For example, a landslide might block the only road to a remote school, preventing students from attending for an extended period. Additionally, the emotional and psychological stress of dealing with the aftermath of a natural disaster can negatively impact a student's ability to focus on their studies (Atlam et al., 2021).

Optimal location for the learning hubs that ensures student accessibility and safety while minimizing exposure to natural hazards, considering student proximity and geographical data

Students residing in mountainous areas of Naguilian, La Union, face significant challenges in accessing educational resources, particularly during natural disasters and other emergencies. Figure 7 illustrates the geographic contribution of these 1,927 students, highlighting the need for strategically placed community-based learning hubs to bridge the gap in school accessibility.

Hence, community learning hubs offer a promising solution to ensure that students in remote areas have continued access to education during crises. These hubs can provide safe and accessible spaces for learning, even when schools are closed or inaccessible. The importance of learning hubs became even more apparent during the COVID-19 pandemic, which forced a rapid transition to emergency remote learning. This abrupt shift presented significant difficulties for students and educators in areas with limited access to technology and infrastructure. For

students in remote, mountainous regions, proximity to emergency learning hubs is critical for ensuring continued education (Bashir et al., 2021).

The proximity of learning hubs to students' residences is a key factor in their effectiveness. When hubs are located close to where students live, they can access these resources more easily, even during emergencies. This is particularly important in mountainous areas, where travel can be challenging and hazardous, especially during natural hazards. As UNICEF (2013) emphasizes, proximity should be a central consideration in the design and implementation of learning hubs.

GIS can be used to analyze students' residential locations and identify optimal sites for learning hubs. By prioritizing areas with high concentrations of students and minimizing travel distances, the hubs can serve as accessible and inclusive spaces for learning continuity during emergencies.

A data-driven approach to site selection, combined with a focus on proximity, can significantly improve the effectiveness of learning hubs in Naguilian, La Union. This approach not only addresses immediate educational needs during crises but also contributes to the long-term resilience of the educational system in disaster-prone regions. By investing in strategically placed learning hubs, Naguilian can ensure that all students have access to quality education, regardless of the challenges they may face.

Figure 7

Mapping the Locations of Students Residing in Mountainous Areas of Naguilian, La Union, Using Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

Figure 8

GIS Mapping of Proposed Learning Hubs in Mountainous Areas of Naguilian, La Union

Figure 9

Proposed Transitional Learning Hubs Mapped on the Geo-Hazard Map of Naguilian, La Union

Figure 10

Proposed Transitional Learning Hubs Mapped on the CLUP of Naguilian, La Union

Figure 11

Student-to-Learning Hub Distances Mapped Using Open Route Service (ORS) in GIS

Figures 8 to 11 illustrate the proposed locations for the transitional learning hubs, a critical aspect of the study. These hubs aim to provide safe and accessible learning spaces for students, particularly during emergencies. Identifying suitable locations required careful consideration, ensuring that each hub is walkable, accessible, and situated in an area with low susceptibility to hazards such as flooding and landslides. To confirm the safety and suitability of the proposed locations, they were overlaid onto the geohazard map and Comprehensive Land Use Plan (CLUP) Map of Naguilian. This analysis verified their resilience to natural hazards and confirmed their compliance with land use regulations.

Table 10

Assessment of Flooding and Landslide Susceptibility at Each Proposed Transitional Learning Hub

LEARNING HUB	SUSCEPTIBILITY LANDSLIDE	SUSCEPTIBILITY TO FLOODING	LAND USE
Learning Hub 1	Low	Not Susceptible	Agricultural
Learning Hub 2	Medium	Not Susceptible	Agricultural
Learning Hub 3	Medium	Not Susceptible	Agricultural
Learning Hub 4	Low	Not Susceptible	Agricultural
Learning Hub 5	Medium	Not Susceptible	Agricultural
Learning Hub 6	Low	Not Susceptible	Agricultural
Learning Hub 7	Low	Not Susceptible	Agricultural

Table 10 reveals that four out of ten proposed transitional learning hub locations are in areas with low susceptibility to landslides and are not susceptible to flooding. However, three out of the seven hubs are located in areas with medium susceptibility to landslides and also not susceptible to flooding. Relocating these three hubs to areas with lower susceptibility to landslides could potentially reduce accessibility for students, as the hubs would be farther away and not within walking distance. The remaining hub, also located in an area with medium landslide susceptibility, is situated in a barangay with both medium and high landslide-prone areas. This presents a challenge in balancing the need for accessibility with the need for safety, a key consideration highlighted in UNICEF's (2013)

guidelines for building transitional learning spaces. These guidelines emphasize the importance of proximity to ensure that students facing difficulties accessing education after natural hazard events can reach these hubs easily.

Figure 11, generated using the Open Routes Servies (ORS) tool in GIS, shows the distances between the transitional learning hubs and the majority of the students they will serve, ranging from 500 meters to 2,400 meters (2.4 kilometers). This range falls within the commonly accepted notion of an ideal walkable distance, which is approximately 2.4 kilometers or a 25 -minute walk (Seneviratne, 1985; Olszewski & Wibowo, 2005). By ensuring that the hubs are located within this walkable distance, the project aims to maximize accessibility for students while also considering their safety by selecting locations with low susceptibility to natural hazards.

Table 12

Shows the Total Number of Students the Learning Hubs Will Serve

LEARNING HUB	NUMBER OF STUDENTS	LOCATION OF LEARNING HUB
Learning Hub 1	146	Mamat-ing Norte
Learning Hub 2	99	Bimmotobot
Learning Hub 3	196	San Antonio
Learning Hub 4	191	Gusing Norte
Learning Hub 5	420	Casilagan
Learning Hub 6	320	Al-Alinao Sur
Learning Hub 7	395	Balecbec

Figure 12 illustrates the final scope of each transitional learning hub. At the same time, Table 11 provides the total number of students assigned to each hub across different barangays. The distribution of students varies across the hubs, ranging from 99 students in TLH 2 (Bimmotobot) to 420 students in TLH 5 (Casilagan). This variation reflects differences in population density and the geographic area served by each hub. Accurately identifying the total number of students per hub is crucial for planning purposes.

As Hussey and Smith (2010) highlight, a detailed analysis of the projected student population is essential to guide the appropriate sizing of the hubs. This involves evaluating enrollment data across various age groups and academic levels to ensure that the hubs can accommodate all learners. Furthermore, Sweigart and Evanovich (2015) emphasize the importance of understanding the diverse needs of the student population when designing transitional learning hubs. This includes considering factors such as access to technology, learning styles, and any special educational needs.

By accurately identifying the total number of students per hub and understanding their diverse needs, planners can ensure appropriate resource allocation and infrastructure planning. This will enable the development of transitional learning hubs that provide a seamless and supportive educational experience for all students, regardless of their academic level or background.

Figure 12

Student Coverage Areas Determined by Distance to Nearest Hub in GIS

Facilities and Areas to be incorporated in the proposed Transitional Learning Center

Figure 13

Students' Preferences for Facilities in Proposed Transitional Learning Hubs in Naguilian's Mountainous Areas

Figure 13 presents student preferences for various features to be integrated into the proposed learning hubs. The most popular preference was a public library, with 80% of the 1,401 students surveyed (1128 students) expressing their desire for this feature. Following closely, 57% (798 students) preferred an outdoor activity space, while 40.9% (573 students) favored a co-working space. Other popular preferences included study cubicles for individual and group activities (38.5% or 539 students), a computer lab (36% or 504 students), and a lecture room (30.5% or 428 students). The least popular preference was an arts and crafts room, with 29.6% (414 students) expressing interest.

Understanding these preferences is crucial for ensuring the effectiveness of the learning hubs and meeting the diverse needs of the students. As Motevalli et al. (2020) emphasize, aligning the hub's offerings with student needs can significantly influence their motivation to learn and engage with the resources provided. By incorporating these preferences into the design and development of the learning hubs, planners can create spaces that foster a positive and productive learning environment for all students.

Vernacular Architecture in Naguilian, La Union

Through casual and informal interviews with residents, students, and barangay officials, bamboo was identified as a

viable local construction material for the proposed project. Its abundance and wide distribution throughout the barangay make it easily accessible and sustainable for construction purposes. Furthermore, the community's familiarity with bamboo enhances its practicality for the project.

Knowledge Gap in Bamboo Construction Techniques

While bamboo is an abundant and sustainable material, the interviews also revealed a lack of standardized or well-defined construction techniques for building bamboo structures within the mountainous barangays of Naguilian, La Union. Specifically, the locals have minimal understanding of critical processes such as bamboo treatment, which is essential for enhancing the material's durability, resistance to pests, and overall structural integrity. As a result, their bamboo constructions are often more vulnerable to wear, decay, and environmental factors, leading to a shorter lifespan and reduced resilience.

Targeted Training Programs for Sustainable Bamboo Construction

This knowledge gap underscores the need for targeted training and education programs to equip the community with the necessary skills and techniques for sustainable and effective bamboo construction practices. By providing training on proper bamboo treatment, construction techniques, and design considerations, the community can harness the full potential of bamboo as a durable and sustainable building material.

Types of Bamboo Available in Naguilian, La Union

According to the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) Region 1, the types of bamboo available in Naguilian, La Union are 'Bayog' (*Bambusa spinosa*) and 'Kawayang Tinik' (*Bambusa blumeana*).

- **Bayog:** This species thrives near water bodies and has long been utilized for construction and other purposes due to its ability to tolerate fluctuations in salinity and water availability.

Kawayang Tinik: This prominent bamboo species is characterized by its impressive size and strength, making it suitable for use as primary structural members in traditional bamboo houses.

Both Bayog and Kawayang Tinik have been traditionally used in the Philippines for various applications, including construction, furniture, and handicrafts. A deeper understanding of their properties and appropriate treatment methods will enable the community to construct more durable, resilient, and sustainable structures using these readily available resources.

ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN SOLUTION

Programmatic and Design Concept

The programmatic and design concepts of this project serve as the fundamental framework that guides the entire development process, starting from the initial conceptualization and schematic drawings to the detailed and precise architectural drawings.

Site Analysis

Plate No.1

Site analysis of Transitional Learning Hub One (1) located in barangay Mamat-ing Norte.

Plate No.2

Site Analysis of Transitional Learning Hub Two (2) Located in Barangay Bimmotobot

Plate No.3

Site Analysis of Transitional Learning Hub Three (3) Located in Barangay San Antonio

Plate No.4

Site Analysis Of Transitional Learning Hub Four (4) Located in Barangay Gusing Norte

Plate No.5

Site Analysis of Transitional Learning Hub Five (5), Located in Barangay Casilagan

Plate No.10

Transitional Learning Hub Floor Plan

Plate No.11

Front Elevation and Rear Elevation of the Transitional Learning Hub

Plate No.12

Right Side View and Left Side View of the Transitional Learning Hub

Plate No. 13

Section thru A and B of the Transitional Learning Hub

Plate No. 14

Exterior Perspective of Transitional Learning Hub

Plate No. 15

Interior Views of Study Area 1 Featuring Learning, Co-Working, Computer, and Arts & Craft Zones

Plate No. 16

Views of the Lecture Room, Public Library Interiors, and Outdoor Activity Space

ARCHITECTURAL CONCEPTUAL DETAIL

Plate No. 17

Design Conceptualization

The municipality of Naguilian, composed of large terrains, is rich in bamboo species, particularly Bayog and Kawayang Tinik, which are widely used for construction and craftsmanship in other places. The design concept of the Transitional Learning Hub originates from the bamboo shoot, inspired by the natural characteristics of bamboo; the structure embodies flexibility, strength, and adaptability—qualities essential for a learning hub located in a disaster-prone area of the municipality. Drawing from the organic form of a bamboo shoot, the architecture incorporates layered, tapering structures that mimic its natural segmentation. In the illustration below, passive cooling is applied, letting the air enter the building and pass through, enhancing natural ventilation and thermal comfort. As the main approach of the project is **community architecture and vernacular architecture**, the design prioritizes locally sourced materials and participatory design processes to ensure that the transitional learning hub is both culturally appropriate and environmentally sustainable. By integrating **Bayog** and **Kawayang Tinik**—native bamboo species abundant in Naguilian—the structure reduces its environmental footprint. It strengthens the connection between the built environment and the local community. The use of bamboo in various architectural elements, such as structural framing, walls, and shading devices, enhances durability while maintaining a lightweight and flexible composition, making it resilient to earthquakes and strong winds.

Structural Systems

Figure 1

Conceptual Structural Systems of the Transitional Learning Hub

(a)

Foundation Design: Integrating Bamboo and Concrete for Structural Stability (Bamboo U, 2024)

(b)

Connection between columns (Bamboo U, 2024)

(c)

Secure Bundling Techniques for Gridshell Construction (Bamboo U, 2024)

(d)

Shear lashing, joining of column and truss (Vaghela, 2013).

(e)

Double and Quadruple Beams-Support (Vaghela, 2013).

a. Foundation Design: Integrating Bamboo and Concrete for Structural Stability

The foundation system integrates Bayog bamboo columns with steel reinforcement bars inside, enhancing load-bearing capacity while maintaining sustainability and aesthetics. The bamboo is securely anchored to a concrete base, with cap holes for mortar infusion, ensuring resilience against wind and seismic forces. To prevent moisture-related degradation, large river stones are embedded between the bamboo and concrete, acting as a protective barrier. This hybrid approach maximizes

the strengths of both bamboo and concrete, creating a durable and structurally sound base for the bamboo dome (Bamboo U, 2024).

b. Connection between columns

This connection is essential for maintaining the integrity and stability of the dome structure, ensuring that the loads are efficiently transferred and distributed. At the heart of the connection is a threaded rod, which serves as a central anchoring point, holding the various components together securely. This rod runs through a central washer and nut, preventing any loosening under stress (Bamboo U, 2024).

c. Secure Bundling Techniques

This structural detail illustrates the method for creating continuous bamboo bundles, which is essential for constructing the grid shell of a bamboo dome. The bamboo culms are overlapped by one meter to ensure a strong and stable connection that can extend to the desired length. The overlapping sections are secured using bamboo pins, which are driven through pre-drilled diagonal holes. These pins provide a traditional and effective means of fastening, leveraging the natural strength of bamboo to create a seamless connection between segments (Bamboo U, 2024).

d. Shear lashing, joining of column and truss

Shear lashing is a traditional binding technique used to securely join two or more bamboo elements, such as columns and trusses, in bamboo construction. This method ensures structural stability, load distribution, and flexibility, making it particularly effective in earthquake-resistant and typhoon-resilient structures (Vaghela, 2013).

e. Double and Quadruple Beams-Support

In bamboo architecture, double and quadruple-beam support systems are used to enhance load-bearing capacity, distribute weight efficiently, and improve structural stability.

These methods are particularly effective in spanning large areas, supporting heavy loads, and reinforcing critical structural joints (Vaghela,2013).

Main Building Material

Figure 2

Actual Image of Bayog A Bamboo Species Abundant in the Municipality of Naguilian

BAYOG

In the Philippines, an endemic bamboo species called Bayog (*Bambusa spinosa*) has long been used for construction. This bamboo species can be found throughout the country, especially near water bodies, and it tolerates changes in salinity and seasonal fluctuations in water availability. It had been called with many scientific names, such as *Bambusa blumeana luzonensis* and *Dendrocalamus merillana*, among others. However, across the county, it is commonly known as Bayog. Bayog has many characteristics similar to the popular *Bambusa blumeana* (Thorny Bamboo/ Kawayan Tinik). Both *Bambusa blumeana* and *Bambusa spinosa* are commonly used in vernacular bamboo houses.

Bayog is a clumping bamboo with erect and sturdy culms that are more or less 20m tall, 8-12cm in diameter, and have

walls up to 4cm thick. The nodes are solitary; the nodal line and nodal ridge are present with aerial roots, especially at the lower nodes. Internodes are green and smooth; the lower ones are up to 30cm long, moderately hollow, and sometimes almost solid at the base. Culm sheaths are 20cm long, 25cm wide, narrowed upward to truncate; the outer surface is strongly ribbed, shortly pubescent with brown to black hairs, while the inner surface is weakly ribbed, shiny, and glabrous. This bamboo is able to tolerate strong annual typhoons. It is able to bend with the wind like a tensioned fishing rod because of its physiology.

Figure 2

Actual Image Of Kawayang Tinik, a Bamboo Species Abundant in the Municipality of Naguilian.

Kawayang Tinik, or *Bambusa blumeana*, is a type of bamboo belonging to the Poaceae family. It typically grows to a height of 15 to 25 meters, with culms (stems) having a diameter of 8 to 15 cm. The internode length ranges from 25 to 35 cm, and the wall thickness is between 10 to 20 mm, becoming thicker toward the base. The plant exhibits a dense clumping growth habit. While it is not inherently invasive, it can spread in certain areas. The culms are characterized by thorny spikes and slightly arching green stems. These culms can vary significantly in diameter and internode length. Clustered branches emerge from the higher nodes, each adorned with tough, sharp thorns. Kawayang Tinik is commonly used in land rehabilitation projects, as well as for creating living fences, windbreaks, or erosion prevention barriers along streams.

CONCLUSIONS

This research highlights the urgent need for community-based learning hubs to mitigate educational disruptions in mountainous regions vulnerable to natural hazards. In these high-risk barangays, students face significant barriers to accessing school, resulting in missed lessons, diminished academic performance, and heightened psychological distress. These challenges create a cycle of educational setbacks, perpetuating inequality and limiting students' potential.

By integrating GIS mapping, the study identified optimal locations for establishing learning hubs that balance accessibility and disaster resilience. This data-driven approach pinpointed safe and accessible areas, ensuring continuity in education during times of crisis. Additionally, the research emphasizes the importance of utilizing locally available materials, such as *bayog* and *kawayang tinik* bamboo, to create sustainable, culturally relevant, and economically viable educational spaces.

Establishing transitional learning hubs offers a dual benefit: addressing the immediate educational challenges posed by natural hazards while contributing to long-term community resilience. These hubs provide a safe and accessible learning environment and serve as models for sustainable development, promoting local capacity building and disaster preparedness. By investing in these hubs, the research advocates for a holistic approach to education that enhances both academic outcomes and community well-being, ensuring that the region's most vulnerable populations can continue to thrive despite the challenges posed by natural hazards.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To effectively implement the proposed transitional learning hubs and ensure their long-term sustainability, the following recommendations are made:

1. Collaboration and Funding: Establish a collaborative framework between government agencies, educational institutions, and local communities to secure funding,

coordinate construction efforts, and ensure ongoing maintenance of the learning hubs. This includes equipping the hubs with necessary learning materials and technology.

2. **Community Engagement:** Prioritize community involvement in the design, construction, and maintenance of the hubs. Engage local artisans, educators, and parents to foster a sense of ownership and ensure the cultural relevance and sustainability of the facilities.

3. **Policy Support:** Advocate for policy support from the Department of Education and local government units to promote the use of alternative learning spaces during disasters and integrate them into the educational system.

Further Research: Conduct further research to assess the long-term educational and social impacts of transitional learning hubs and refine strategies for their implementation in other hazard-prone areas. This includes evaluating the effectiveness of the hubs in mitigating learning disruptions, improving academic performance, and promoting community resilience.

By addressing these recommendations, this study aims to contribute to a more resilient and inclusive educational system in Naguilian, La Union, ensuring uninterrupted learning opportunities for students in far-flung and disaster-prone areas.

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